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ABSTRACT

Though Marine Parks in Malaysia are important to protect important marine resources, however, it is degraded due to human activities. In order to properly manage marine parks, economic valuation is necessary to understand the importance of marine resources conservation activities. In this study, tourist's willingness to pay (WTP) to protect marine resources at Pulau Perhentian Marine Park (PPMP) was carried out with contingent valuation method. Both single-bounded and double-bounded dichotomous choice contingent valuation methods were used to estimate tourists WTP. A total of 250 tourists were interviewed. The results showed that median WTP ranged between RM17.98 to RM21.72 and based on the number of tourist's arrivals in 2011, the aggregate benefit at PPMP would be ranged from 1.62 to 1.96 million, respectively. The results of the study could be beneficial to the Marine Park authority in setting appropriate entrance fee at PPMP and taking the adequate conservation activities to protect marine environment and resources to deteriorate further.

Keywords: Marine parks, contingent valuation method, willingness to pay, dichotomous choice, conservation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Malaysia is one of the most popular tourism countries in the world. Tourism is the second largest foreign exchange earning sector Hanafiah et al. (2010). Tourism helps to promote countries infrastructural development, attracts foreign investment, creates employment opportunities, develops more domestic industries, and enable the exchange of knowledge and technology. The Marine Parks of Malaysia have become an important part of tourism industry that generates foreign exchange earnings. Marine Parks are popular due to eco-tourism activities, provide habitats for marine resources, protect environment, generate livelihoods for local communities, and earn revenues for the government. Marine recreational activities that consist of sight-seeing, diving and snorkelling have great value in the tourism industry. The total number of visitors was doubled from 423,229 in 2000 to 793,359 in 2013 in marine parks located in the States of Kedah, Terengganu, Pahang, and Johor in Peninsular Malaysia (Department of Marine Park Malaysia, 2014), contributing revenues and incomes to the Malaysian economy.

However, rapid tourism development has both positive and negative impacts on the society. Tourism contributes significantly to the economy while coastal development as a result of rapid tourism development has degraded some of the important marine resources. Reef Check Malaysia, 2010 reported that average cover of nutrient indicator algae which is harmful for corals growth is relatively high in Peninsular Malaysia compared to East Malaysia, at 7.2 and 3.8%, respectively. The main reason for this problem is due to the large number of resorts found in the marine parks off the East coast of Peninsular Malaysia where tourism industry has expanded more rapidly compared to those in East Malaysia. Therefore, proper management of the resources is essential to ensure the long-run and sustainable generation of benefits.

As a current management practice, 'Conservation Fee' is collected from tourists for the conservation activities of marine resources in marine parks of Malaysia. This conservation fee in the form of an entry fee was initiated since 1999. The fee is collected and used in the maintenance and protection of Marine Parks Yeo (2002). A uniform conservation fee is charged for the local and foreign tourists. The fee for an adult visitor is RM5.00 (US\$1.32)

whereas that for a student, a retiree and a child is charged RM 2.50. The Worldwide Fund for Nature, 2009 (WWF, Malaysia) states that majority of the Marine Parks in Malaysia have insufficient fund for conservation activities. The entry fee currently imposed on tourists to marine parks is minimal and uniform for all groups. This study attempts to seek the answer to the question of whether visitors are willing to pay more than the current fee levied in order to protect the coral resources and the environment of the Pulau Perhentian Marine Park (PPMP) in Terengganu.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

PPMP comprises a globally important area of marine species biodiversity. It is situated in the South China Sea, approximately 10 nautical miles off the coast of the state of Terengganu. There are 11 islands that constituted the Perhentian with the largest being Pulau Besar (approximately 867 ha) and Pulau Kecil (approximately 524 ha) (Figure 1). Other important islands are Pulau Rawa, Pulau Serenggeh, Pulau Susu Dara Besar and Pulau Susu Dara Kecil. The marine park has the most renowned and beautiful islands in Malaysia. There are plenty of palm trees, crystal-clear water, blue oceans, sea-turtles, jellyfish, small sharks, reef-fishes, soft powdery sands, and fringing coral reefs found in the islands. PPMP was first initiated as marine protected areas in 1983 under the Department of Fisheries Malaysia (DoFM) and gazetted as Marine Park in 1994 under the establishment of Marine Park Malaysia Order 1994 (Fisheries Act 1995). Fishing is prohibited within two nautical miles from the lowest water level seaward. The islands' only small village is 'kampung pasir huntu' being located in Pulau Perhentian Kecil. This village is home to over more than 1500 people. A study by Coral Cay Conservation in 2000 around the adjacent Marine Park Islands along this eastern coastline recorded 221 hard coral species and 127 fish species Harborne et al. (2000). The number of fish species was recorded 127. The reefs around the Perhentian Islands may support up to 80% of the biodiversity Kaur and Barison (2008). In comparison with the reef systems of the other Marine Park Islands on the east coast of Peninsular Malaysia, the coral reefs around PPMP are recognized to contain high biodiversity.

Prior to early 1980s, the main economic activities on the islands were fishing and small scale agriculture including the cultivation of coconut, rubber, clove and fruit trees. Although tourism has started in 1960s, it has developed into a major economic activity in PPMP only recently. The most popular tourist's areas are Teluk Pauh, Pasir Jong, Teluk Keke and Teluk dalam in Pulau Perhentian Besar and Kampung Pasir Panjang, Teluk Kerma, and a few other areas in Pulau Perhentian Kecil. The most popular tourist's activities in PPMP are scuba-diving, snorkeling and swimming. PPMP receives up to 90,150 tourists annually. The number of tourists is almost double from 2004 to 2011 (Figure 2) Islam et al. (2013).

Figure 1. Pulau Perhentian Marine Park (PPMP) Malaysia.

Source: Islam et al. (2013)

Figure: 2 Total numbers of tourists in PPMP from 2004 to 2011.

Source: Islam et al. (2013)

2.2 The valuation approach of CVM

This study estimates the tourist's willingness to pay (WTP) to protect marine resources by using a Contingent Valuation Method (CVM). The CVM comes under the hypothetical classification Mitchell and Carson (1989), to estimate economic values for environmental goods and services. In contingent valuation method, people are directly ask to state how much they would be willing to pay (WTP) for specific environmental services or willing to accept (WTA) to give up specific environmental services in a survey.

WTP can be elicited by different elicitation format. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) panel of economic experts Arrow et al. (1993) suggested take-it-or-leave-it approach (or single-bounded dichotomous choice approach) format in CVM. This method is the most commonly used because respondents find it easier to make their decisions with discrete choices in market transactions Lee (1997). Moreover, according to Hanemann, 1991 double-bounded dichotomous choice approach is more efficient than others. Therefore, both single and double-bounded format were used in this research. In single-bound CVM, both logit and probit model were used due to dichotomous dependent variable. However, log-logistic and log-normal model were used for double-bound CVM.

Model Specification

The estimation procedure is closely followed used in the study by Hanemann (1984). The respondents WTP in PPMP depend on the relevant environmental quality and their income. Then the individual's utility function will be

$$u = v(Q_j, Y, S) \quad (j=0, 1) \quad (1)$$

where, Q is the quality of the environment and if $j=0$, Q is reduced, while if $j=1$, then Q is increased or maintained. Y represents income and S indicates the socioeconomic characteristics and other observable attributes which might affect individual's preferences.

If the quality of environment is increased or maintained, the individual utility function will be

$$u_1 = (1, Y, S) \text{ and} \\ u_0 = (0, Y, S) \text{ if the quality is decreased}$$

Individual's utility function cannot be seen totally due to some unobservable components. Now, the utility function will be

$$u(Q_j, Y, S) = v(Q_j, Y, S) + \varepsilon_j \quad (j= 0, 1) \quad (2)$$

where, ε_j is the stochastic error term and both ε_0 and ε_1 are independent with zero means.

An individual is required to pay a given amount (A) due to improvement in the quality of environment of PPMP. The respondent will agree to pay if

$$v(1, Y-A, S) + \varepsilon_1 > v(0, Y, S) + \varepsilon_0 \quad (3)$$

Otherwise, respondents will refuse to pay.

The probability of 'yes' response is presented as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_i &= \Pr \{ \text{Yes response} \} \\ &= \Pr \{ v(1, Y-A, S) + \varepsilon_1 > v(0, Y, S) + \varepsilon_0 \} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The probability of 'no' response is:

$$\begin{aligned} P_0 &= \Pr \{ \text{No response} \} \\ &= 1 - P_i \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The random variable can be defined as $\square = \varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_0$. If we determined the utility difference by $\Delta v = v(1, Y-A, S) - v(0, Y, S)$ then we can write equation is

$$P_i = F_{\square}(\Delta v) \quad (6)$$

Assuming that ε follows a logistic regression, then we can write equation

$$\begin{aligned} P_i &= F_{\square}(\Delta v) \\ &= 1 / (1 + \exp^{-\Delta v}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

An individual would agree to pay if their WTP is greater than the posted amount. The probability of 'yes' for a given amount 'A' is represented by

$$\begin{aligned} P_i &= \Pr(WTP > A) \\ &= 1 / (1 + \exp^{-\Delta v}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Then, the probability of WTP is less than or equal to A is given by A

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(WTP \leq A) &\equiv G(A) \\ &= 1 - [1 / (1 + \exp^{-\Delta v})] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where, $G(\bullet)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the WTP.

The logit model in this study takes the following form:

$$P_i = E(Y_i = 1/X_i) = 1 / [1 + \exp - (\beta_0 + \beta_1 BID_i + \beta_k X_{ik} + \varepsilon_i)] \quad (10)$$

where, P_i is the probability that $Y_i = 1$ (Yes response), BID_i is the bid amount, X_i is the vector of independent variables that influence the probability, i is the individual observations, β_0 is the intercept, β_1 , and β_k are parameters of bid, and independent variables, respectively and ε_i error term follows a normal distribution with a mean zero and variance σ^2 .

The Probit model uses a CDF of standard normal distribution. Assuming a linear relationship between n_i and the independent variables

$$n_i = \sum_{k=1}^k \beta_0 + \beta_1 BID_i + \beta_k X_{ik} + \varepsilon_i \quad (11)$$

now, $n_i = \text{probit}(p_i) = \Phi^{-1} p_i$

where, $\Phi(n_i) = \int_{-\infty}^{n_i} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp(-\frac{1}{2} u^2) du$

Or $p_i = \Phi \sum_{k=1}^k \beta_0 + \beta_1 BID_i + \beta_k X_{ik} + \varepsilon_i$

The expected value or mean of WTP is calculated by Cameron (1988) and the median is calculated using formula from Hanemann et al. (1991);

$$\text{Mean WTP} = \frac{\beta_0 + \sum \beta_k X_{ik}}{-\beta_1} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Median WTP} = \beta_0 + \beta_k * X_{ik} / -\beta_1 \quad (13)$$

where, β_1 is the parameter for the bid amount. β_0 and β_k are the estimated constant and the estimated parameters of coefficients respectively, and X_{ik} are the mean values of the respective independent variables.

Double-bounded dichotomous choice (DBDC)

The DBDC format is an extension of SBDC. Following Hanemann, et al. (1991), this estimation procedure involves respondents being presented with two levels of bids where the second bid is contingent upon the response to the first bid. If the individual responds "yes" to the first bid (BID_1), the second bid (denoted BID_u) is an amount greater than the first bid ($BID_u > BID_1$); if the individual responds "no" to the first bid (BID_1), the second bid (BID_L) is some amount smaller than the first bid ($BID_L < BID_1$).

In this research, respondent will be asked whether he/she would be willing to pay the first bid amount for the improving condition of the PMP. If the answer is yes, then a second higher bid amount will be presented. If the answer is no, then a second lower bid amount will be given. Thus, four possible outcomes will be derived with different probabilities. The outcomes are (a) both answers are "yes"; (b) both answers are "no"; (c) a "yes" followed by a "no"; and (d) a "no" followed by a "yes". The outcomes are denoted by π^{yy} , π^{nn} , π^{yn} , π^{ny} , respectively. According to Hanemann (1991) the outcomes of the probabilities are derived from the following equations:

$$\text{Prob (yes, yes)} = \pi^{yy} = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1 BID_u + \beta_i X_i)} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Prob (yes, no)} = \pi^{yn} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1 BID_u + \beta_i X_i)} - \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1 BID_1 + \beta_i X_i)} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{Prob (no, yes)} = \pi^{ny} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1 BID_1 + \beta_i X_i)} - \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1 BID_L + \beta_i X_i)} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Prob (no, no)} = \pi^{nn} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1 BID_L + \beta_i X_i)} \quad (17)$$

where, BID_1 is the initial bid, BID_u is the higher bid, BID_L is the lower bid, α is the intercept, β_1 is the coefficient estimate of the bid amount, β_s are the coefficients of other independent variables in above four equations (14), (15), (16), and (17). The double-bounded dichotomous choice model is estimated using log-normal and also log-logistic form.

The mean for the double bounded approach is calculated as the area under the probability function of accepting the bid. The area shows the proportion of the population who would consume the good at each price level, and their associated utility. It can be expressed as:

$$E(WTP) = \int_L^U (1 + e^{a+bWILLING})^{-1} db \quad (18)$$

where, $(1 + e^{a+bWILLING})^{-1}$ is the probability of saying "yes" and U and L are the upper and lower limits of the integration respectively. Whereas the median is as follows:

$$\text{Median} = \alpha / \beta_1 \quad (19)$$

The descriptions of explanatory variables are presented in Table 1. Due to large numbers of attribute variables, factor analysis was carried out. Factor analysis is a technique to reduce and sort large numbers of attribute variables and scaling of data (from 5 strongly agree to 1 strongly disagree). This method mainly used to find out the similarities of the variables that are highly correlated with each other and form groups into smaller amount of factors Bortz (2005).

Table 1. Variable Name and description

Variable name	Variable description
WILLING	Dependent variable, willing = 1 if the respondents are willing to pay for the amount ask to them, 0 = otherwise
LOCAL	1 if respondent is from Malaysia (local tourists), 0 otherwise
MALE	1 if male, 0 if female
AGE	Respondents age
OCCUPATION	1 if respondent is employed, 0 otherwise
INCOME	Monthly income of the respondent in Malaysian Ringgit
WATERQUA	Respondent's opinion on the water of PPMP is very clear, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
FISHSPEC	Respondent's opinion on the many fish species of PPMP, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
CORALS	Respondent's opinion on the PPMP is rich in different types of corals, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
TURTLES	Respondent's opinion on the many turtles found in PPMP, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
BEACHQUA	Respondent's opinion on the beaches of PPMP are neat and clean, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
CROWD	Respondent's opinion on the PPMP is not too crowded, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
DEVELOPM	Respondent's opinion on PPMP is well developed Island, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
INFRASTRUCTURE	Respondent's opinion on the infrastructural facilities of PPMP is very good, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
ACCESSIBILITY	Respondent's opinion on accessibility of PPMP is very convenient, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
SECURITY	Respondent's opinion on PPMP is very secured place to visit, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
OVERALL	Respondent's opinion on the overall environment of PPMP is very good, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = no opinion, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree
VISITS	1 respondents visited PPMP for the first time, 0 otherwise
BID	Dichotomous choice bids, there are five sets of bid; RM10, RM15, RM20, RM25, and RM30

2.3. Survey design

The target population of this study was tourists' visiting at PPMP. Tourists involved in diving and snorkeling activities can get direct use benefits. However, those who does not involve in these activities, have non-use value implying that marine park resources should be preserved for future generations. CVM can capture both the use and non-use values. Therefore, all tourists (users, non-users, locals and foreign tourists) were included in this research.

Before the final survey, a pre-survey was carried out in April, 2013. The pre-survey was conducted to get an overall idea about the study site, selection of the interview locations, pre-testing of questionnaire, and to determine the bid levels. The final survey was conducted in the month of June, as this is the month of peak tourist arrivals at PPMP. The survey was conducted at different locations in both Pulau Perhentian Besar and Kecil.

The sample size depends on the elicitation methods used in CVM. Generally, CVM studies require large sample size because of large variation in WTP responses Mitchell and Carson (1989). Calia and Strazzera (1998) recommended 100 or less samples as □small size□, 250 – 400 as □medium size□; and more than 1000 as □large size□. The study also concluded that medium sample size performed well in both single and double bound CVM method for providing point estimates for the parameters and of the mean WTP. Therefore, in this study, a minimum of 250 tourists were interviewed by convenience sampling method.

The survey questionnaires includes information on socio-economic characteristics of the respondents such as country of origin, sex, age, highest education level attained, annual household income, and occupation. Other questions include tourist's perception on different resource attributes and facilities of PPMP. Five different bids RM10.00, RM15.00, RM20.00, RM25.00, and RM30.00 were used in the questionnaire based on pre-survey. In the single-bounded dichotomous choice format (SBDC), respondents was asked whether they would be willing or not to

pay an increasing entry fee to contribute to conservation activities in PPMP. The format of the single-bounded dichotomous choice was as follows:

The respondents were asked 'If the Marine Park Department charges RM__ as an entry fee for the conservation activities in this park, would you be willing to pay for it?'

Yes No

Each respondent was asked only one offer, selected randomly from the above stated range (RM10.00 to RM30.00) of offers. Randomly selected price for different respondents generated price variation. In the SBDC format, respondents can understand what purposes they are paying for and it is easy for them to provide the answer as they are not required to determine their exact willingness to pay rather just to know whether they are willing to pay at least this amount Ahmad (2009). In double-bounded dichotomous choice format, a respondent were asked to increase the WTP if he/she answer 'yes' or to decrease the amount if the answer is 'no'. The tourists were asked to accept or reject the proposed levels. The details of the bids were shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Different bids used in double-bound CVM.

First bid	Upper bid	Lower bid
10	15	8
15	20	10
20	25	15
25	30	20
30	35	25

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Profile of Respondents

The respondent's socio demographic profile is shown in Table 3. As shown in Table 3, the number of male tourists (53.6%) was higher than female counterparts (46.4%). The average age of tourists was below 30 and the ranged from 18 to 65 years. The tourists visiting PPMP were highly educated with more than half of them (54.8%) were university graduate. After that the tourists had technical diploma (26%), followed by secondary education (16.4%), while only few 0.8% of the tourists had no formal education. Most tourists (58%) were private employees, 15.6% business owner, and 10% civil servants and part-time workers. Only 3.2% of the total tourists were non-working spouse and retirees. The majority of the tourists (32.4%) have monthly income more than RM5000.00, while 28% of them have monthly income between RM3000.00 and RM4999.00. Only 6.8% of the tourists have monthly income below RM500.00.

3.2. WTP Estimation

The results from the CVM studies were analysed by using both single and double-bounded dichotomous choice model. The data analysis was carried out by LIMDEP, NLogit Version 4. The single-bound choice model was estimated by both logit and probit model, while log-logistic and log-normal models were used to analyse double-bound CVM. The dependent variable is willingness to pay and the explanatory variables were determined on the basis of the importance to estimate WTP. The explanatory variables included in the model are listed below:

Willingness = $\alpha + \beta_1 \text{ LOCAL} + \beta_2 \text{ MALE} + \beta_3 \text{ AGE} + \beta_4 \text{ OCCUPATION} + \beta_5 \text{ INCOME} + \beta_6 \text{ WATERQUA} + \beta_7 \text{ FISHSPEC} + \beta_8 \text{ CORALS} + \beta_9 \text{ TURTLES} + \beta_{10} \text{ CROWD} + \beta_{11} \text{ BEACHQUA} + \beta_{12} \text{ DEVELOPM} + \beta_{13} \text{ INFRASTRUCTURE} + \beta_{14} \text{ ACCESSIBILITY} + \beta_{15} \text{ SECURITY} + \beta_{16} \text{ OVERALL} + \beta_{17} \text{ VISITS} + \beta_{18} \text{ BID}$
(20)

Table 3: Characteristics of respondents based on socio-economic background

Variables	Category	Tourists (n=250)	
		No	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	134	53.6
	Female	116	46.4
Age group	18-20	18	7.2
	21-30	157	62.8
	31-40	54	21.6
	41-60	18	7.2
	> 60	3	1.2
Education attainment	No formal schooling	2	0.8
	Primary	5	2.0
	Secondary	41	16.4
	Diploma	65	26.0
	University	137	54.8
Type of Profession	Civil Servant	25	10
	Own business	39	15.6
	Private employee	145	58
	Labourer	7	2.8
	Part-time workers	26	10.4
	Retired	5	2
	Non-working Spouse	3	1.2
Monthly income (RM)	<RM500	17	6.8
	RM500-1499	26	10.4
	RM1500-2999	56	22.4
	RM3000-4999	70	28
	≥RM5000	81	32.4

A total of 18 explanatory variables are included in the econometric analysis which is in equation 20. Due to the large number of attribute variables and scaling of data (from 5 strongly agree to 1 strongly disagree), factor analysis is used to reduce and sort the large number of variables. The result of the factor analysis is shown in Table 4. There are three factors found as seen in Table 4. The items scoring above 0.4 formed the group of factor1, factor2, and factor3. In the first factor, the variables infrastructure, security, development, beach quality, and accessibility named as physical attribute index. In the second factor, the variables are fish species, corals, turtle's, and water quality named as resource attribute index. The variables crowd level, overall environment formed the congestion attribute index.

Therefore, factor1 (physical attribute index), factor2 (resource attribute index), and factor3 (congestion attribute index) represented by F1, F2, and F3, respectively are used in the place of the variables in equation 20 which is shown in equation 21.

$$\text{Willingness} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{LOCAL} + \beta_2 \text{MALE} + \beta_3 \text{AGE} + \beta_5 \text{OCCUPATION} + \beta_6 \text{INCOME} + \beta_7 \text{F1} + \beta_8 \text{F2} + \beta_9 \text{F3} + \beta_{10} \text{VISITS} + \beta_{11} \text{BID} \quad (21)$$

Expected sign of these variables and factors are shown in Table 5. In this study, it is expected that WTP to be positively related with occupation, income, physical attribute index, resource attribute index, and visit. It is expected that the people who are employed and with higher income group, are likely to have a high probability to say yes to the offered bid amount. Previous literature also found this type of relationship (Brox *et al.*, 2003; Collins *et al.*, 2005; Stumborg *et al.*, 2001; Whitehead, 2000). Physical attribute index is also expected to be positively related with WTP because tourists who found the infrastructure, security, development, beach quality, and accessibility of PPMP are in good condition, people are willing to pay more due to their satisfaction. Similarly, the tourists who found fish species, corals, turtle's, and water quality are in good condition, the probability if saying yes will be increase with the offered bid amount. It is also expected that people who visited the PPMP for the first time, are willing to more because the tourists visited for the second time will get less satisfaction due to the pollution of PPMP. However, the variable local is expected to have negative relationship with the WTP because local people are less willing to pay to the offered bid amount compared to foreigner. Previous literature showed that foreign people are willing to pay more compared to locals (Nam and Son, 2001; Ayob *et al.*, 2002). It is also expected that utility level will be decreased if the crowd level

is increased. The sign of bid amounts is expected to be negative because of tourists WTP will be decreased as the bid amount increases. Uncertainty arises for male and age because of different arguments can be made for these variables.

Table 4. Factor Analysis of Different Attribute Variables (Principal Component Analysis - Varimax Rotated)

Variables	Components		
	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3
Infrastructure	0.760		
Security	0.727		
Development	0.700		
Clean beach	0.684		
Accessibility	0.581		
Fish Species		0.869	
Corals		0.805	
Turtles		0.624	
Water quality		0.535	0.531
Crowd level			0.698
Overall environment			0.660

Table 5. Variable Name and Expected Sign

Variable name	Expected sign
WILLING	+
LOCAL	-
MALE	(?)
AGE	(?)
OCCUPATION	+
INCOME	+
F1	+
F2	+
F3	-
VISIT	+
BID	-

WTP Estimation by Single and Double bounded Model

In single-bound CVM, the study used both logit and probit models. The percentage of correct prediction in logit model (71.6%) show better results than probit model (71.2%) (Table 6). This result is also consistent with previous studies (Loomis *et al.*, 2000; Ahmad, 2009).

The coefficient estimates of probit model shows better results than logit model in terms of Chi-squared test and McFadden Pseudo R² value. The Chi-squared and McFadden Pseudo R² value of probit model 67.32 and 0.194 were slightly higher than logit model 66.91 and 0.193 respectively.

The results of the probit model show that bid1 and income are highly significant at 1% level, while local, age, occupation, and resource attribute index are significant at 5% level. The signs of coefficients of the most variables in both models are same as it is expected.

The negative sign for the bid coefficient indicates that the probability of yes response decreases as bid level increases. Earlier studies (Mamat, 2010; Ahmad, 2009; Radam and Mansor, 2005) also showed the negative sign of the bid coefficient. The local tourists were negatively related with the offered bid amount means local tourists were less likely to say 'yes' to the amount offered to them consistent with the previous study Yacob *et al.*, 2009. Male shows a negative sign which means male are less likely to pay the offered bid amounts. The coefficient for age is negative indicating that older tourists are less likely to pay compared to younger tourists which may be due to younger generation is more concerned about the environment. The occupation and income show positive coefficients which indicate that holding other variables constant the probability of 'yes' response increases for those who are employed and wealthier. Previous studies (Radam and Mansor, 2005; Mamat, 2010) also showed income and occupation were positively related with WTP. The physical attribute index shows a positive sign means respondents

who found the development, infrastructure, accessibility, security and beach quality of PPMP is good, are willing to pay more may be due to their satisfaction. The resource attribute index water quality, fish diversities, corals varieties, turtles availability show positive sign means respondents who found the resources are good in condition would be willing to pay more may be due to their satisfaction in the state the resources. The congestion attribute index is negatively related with the probability of 'yes' means the respondents who found PPMP is too crowded is less likely to pay. The positive sign for visits indicates the tourists who visited PPMP for the first time are more likely to say 'yes' to the offered bid amount. Logit model also provides similar results in terms of significance levels and sign.

In double-bound CVM, the coefficient estimates of the log-logistic model show better fit than log-normal model because the chi-squared value of log-logistic model (565.173) is higher than that of log-normal model (564.204). Ahmad (2009) also found that log-logistic model had better fit than log-normal model.

Similar with single-bound model, all variables are significant except resource attribute index. Table 6 shows bid and income are highly significant at 1% level, while the variables local, age, and occupation are significant at 5% level in both log-logistic and log-normal models. Both log-logistic and log-normal model show similar results in terms of sign and significant levels.

Table 6. The estimated parameters of single and double-bound models at PPMP

Variables	Coefficient of the models			
	Single-bound		Double-bound	
	Probit	Logit	Log-logistic	Log-normal
Constant	-0.670 (-0.753)	-1.137 (-0.773)	3.752** (2.569)	2.310*** (2.584)
bid	-0.055*** (-4.158)	-0.089*** (-4.028)	-2.252*** (-9.023)	-1.361*** (-9.542)
local	-0.379** (-1.994)	-0.634** (-2.020)	-0.598** (-2.097)	-0.369** (-2.108)
male	-0.047 (-0.266)	-0.089 (-0.303)	-0.057 (-0.219)	-0.032 (-0.200)
age	-0.023** (-2.196)	-0.037** (-2.172)	-0.032** (-2.118)	-0.019** (-2.132)
occupation	0.453** (2.230)	0.779** (2.285)	0.667** (2.287)	0.390** (2.227)
income	0.384*** (4.605)	0.636*** (4.480)	0.572*** (4.626)	0.338*** (4.681)
resource attribute index	0.065** (2.095)	0.101** (1.960)	0.067 (1.432)	0.042 (1.490)
physical attribute index	0.015 (0.563)	0.025 (0.565)	0.009 (0.257)	0.006 (0.281)
congestion attribute index	-0.054 (-0.770)	-0.082 (-0.699)	-0.019 (-0.198)	-0.009 (-0.149)
visit	0.059 (0.310)	0.096 (0.294)	0.062 (0.218)	0.018 (0.108)
Log likelihood	-139.557	-139.759	282.586	282.102
McFadden Pseudo R-squared	0.194	0.193		
Number of observation	250	250	250	250
Chi squared	67.32	66.91	565.173	564.204
Correct prediction	71.20%	71.60%		

Note: Figure in the parentheses is t-ratio

***, **, denotes 1% ($P \leq 0.01$), and 5% ($P \leq 0.05$) of significant level respectively.

The variable local is negatively related with the probability of saying 'yes' response indicating that local tourists are less willing to pay than foreign tourists. The negative sign of variable age means older people are less willing to pay to protect marine resources. Income and occupation show positive signs indicating that the probability of 'yes' response increases with the increase in respondent's income level and respondents who are employed. The positive sign for the resource attribute index means respondents who think the resources are in good condition are willing to pay more. The physical attribute index has a positive sign which means respondents' who are satisfied with the physical facilities of PPMP, are willing to pay more. The signs for all variables are the same as the single-bound model (Ahmad, 2009).

3.3. Calculation of Welfare in terms of Mean and median of WTP

In order to estimate the welfare, mean or median of WTP can be used Ahmad (2009). The mean and median WTP calculated from four methods namely, logit, probit, log-logistic and log-normal are shown in Table 7. The mean and median WTP shows different values in different models. In single-bound model, median values are slightly higher than mean values in both logit and probit models. However, in double-bounded CVM, median WTP are lower compared to mean.

The log-normal model showed the highest mean WTP in RM23.32. Mamat (2010) also showed the highest mean WTP estimates in case of log-normal model. However, probit model showed the highest Median WTP in RM21.72. In both mean and median WTP values, median is more consistent compared to mean for example, mean value of log-logistic and log-normal models were RM21.62 and RM23.32 respectively. However, the median values of log-logistic and log-normal models were RM17.98 and RM18.11, respectively which was more consistent compared to mean WTP.

Table 7. Mean and median WTP of different models from CVM method

Model		All	
		Mean	Median
Single-bound	Logit	20.692	21.442
	Probit	20.799	21.721
Double-bound	Log-logistic	21.617	17.980
	Log-normal	23.321	18.111

3.4. Aggregated Benefits of PPMP

The aggregate benefit of PPMP can be obtained by multiplying the individual WTP derived from the analysis with the total number of tourists. The yearly benefit was calculated for the years between 2004 and 2011 as shown in Table 8.

This study used median WTP to calculate the aggregate conservation benefit of PPMP because median value is more consistent compared to mean Hanemann (1984). According to Hanemann (1984), median is generally more robust measure of central tendency. The consistency of median value also found from this study (Table 7). In 2004, the expected the aggregated benefit of PPMP is ranged between 0.92 million and 1.11 million. This expected aggregated benefit is almost increasing in every year. In 2011, the expected aggregated benefit of PPMP of logit model is RM1.93 million, followed by RM1.96 million for the probit model. The log-logistic and log-normal models calculated the aggregated benefits are RM1.62 million and RM1.63 million respectively. Since, the highest median WTP of PPMP is estimated at RM21.72, this WTP value the authority could be used as entry fee instead of current entry fee RM5.00 to raise the conservation fund to protect marine resources.

Table 8. Estimated conservation benefits of PPMP from different model for all tourists

Year	No of tourists	Logit	Probit	Log-logistic	Log-normal
		WTP = 21.44	WTP= 21.72	WTP= 17.98	WTP = 18.11
2004	51150	1096656	1110978	919677	926326.5
2005	47527	1018979	1032286	854535.5	860714
2006	59172	1268648	1285216	1063913	1071605
2007	58546	1255226	1271619	1052657	1060268
2008	75262	1613617	1634691	1353211	1362995
2009	89968	1928914	1954105	1617625	1629320
2010	93541	2005519	2031711	1681867	1694028
2011	90150	1932816	1958058	1620897	1632617

Data Source: Islam *et al.*, 2013.

4. CONCLUSION

The objective of the study was to estimate the WTP to conserve the marine resources of PPMP. PPMP, the popular tourists' destination in Malaysia is one of the most degraded marine parks due to pollution. The results of this study could be beneficial to the park authority to determine the appropriate entrance fee. The appropriate entrance fee could be able to make conservation activities properly at PPMP. The estimated median WTP from this study ranged from RM17.98-RM21.72 and based on the number of tourists arrivals in 2011, the aggregate amount of entrance fee collected ranged from 1.62 million to 1.96 million which is much higher compared to the collection of only 0.45 million based on the current entry fee of RM5.00. This study recommends RM21.72 may apply as an entry fee. Therefore, marine park authorities could consider an increased amount of entry fee instead of current entrance fee to carry out the conservation activities of PPMP properly. This increasing aggregated benefit could solve the arising various issues and problems of PPMP like lack of financial constraint to maintain the management activities for sustainable tourism development at PPMP. This study also may help to understand the policy maker or the park authorities about the necessities of economic valuation studies to estimate the aggregate conservation benefit of natural resources for long-run balanced economic growth at PPMP. Moreover, policy makers could be able to take their decision based on the priority actions for proper planning in future.

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